

Table 2. Effect of *T. viride* alone and with cytozyme on ShB infection. Assam, India, 1983.

Treatment	Sheaths infected (%)
Inoculation with <i>R. solani</i> alone	74.6
Inoculation with <i>R. solani</i> + <i>T. viride</i>	60.3
Inoculation with <i>R. solani</i> + <i>T. viride</i> with 2 h cytozyme dip	90.0
LSD (0.05)	14.5
CV (%)	12.1

The root dip was prepared by mixing 2 ml cytozyme with 24 ml water. Seedling roots were dipped for 5 min and 2 h the first year and for 2 h the second year, then air-dried for 2 h. Rice variety Pusa 2-21 was transplanted 18 Aug 1982, 25 d after seeding (DAS), at 4 seedlings/pot in inoculated soil (inoculum in maize-meal sand medium added at 5% of soil). Mahsuri was transplanted on 2 Aug 1983, 25 DAS.

Although cytozyme reduced ShB infection 1.5 mo after inoculation, the difference disappeared at 2.5 mo (Table 1). ShB suppression was more pronounced with *T. viride* than with cytozyme. However, the effect of *T. viride* was not pronounced on Mahsuri in 1983 (Table 2). When *T. viride* was used with cytozyme, its suppressing effect was nullified. □

Host plants of rice grassy stunt virus (GSV)

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We inoculated seedlings of 4 *Oryza* spp. and 18 weed species by confining separately in cages for 1 d with 20 brown planthoppers *Nilaparvata lugens* that had fed on plants infected with GSV strain 2. Inoculated plants were indexed by ELISA 1 mo later. Extracts of plants with absorbance at 405 nm higher than 3 times that of uninoculated plant extracts were considered to contain the virus.

All rices and five weed species were infected (see table). The infected rices showed typical GSV symptoms. None of the infected weeds showed clear

Absorbance at 405 nm in ELISA of extracts of plants infected with GSV after inoculation by GSV-viruliferous BPH. IRRI.

Species	Inoculated plants (no.)	Infected plants (no.)	Absorbance at 405 nm	
			Infected plants	Uninoculated plants (mean)
<i>Oryza australiensis</i>				
Acc. 100882	14	6	0.08–1.40	0.00
Acc. 101144	9	3	0.16–0.32	0.00
Acc. 101397	5	3	0.19–0.99	0.00
<i>O. barthii</i>	3	2	0.68–1.14	0.04
<i>O. latifolia</i>	10	4	0.27–0.70	0.03
<i>O. longistaminata</i>	3	3	0.09–0.33	0.00
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	10	4	0.05–0.14	0.01
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>	9	5	0.24–0.96	0.05
<i>Echinochloa colona</i>	10	2	0.08–0.40	0.02
<i>Leersia hexandra</i>	10	2	0.07–0.13	0.02
<i>Monochoria vaginalis</i>	10	1	0.10	0.03

symptoms. Weeds not infected with GSV were *Axonopus compressus*, *Brachiaria distachya*, *B. mutica*, *Chloris barbata*, *Digitaria ciliaris*, *Eleusine*

indica, *Eragrostis tenella*, *Fimbristylis miliacea*, *Imperata cylindrica*, *Leptochloa chinensis*, *Paspalidium flavidum*, and *Paspalum conjugatum*. □

Fungicides to control rice sheath blight (ShB)

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It has been difficult to find a good source of resistance to rice ShB caused by *Rhizoctonia solani*. We tested seven chemicals during transplanted aman season (Jul–Nov) 1987 on the BRRI farm. The experiment was set up in 3- × 2-m plots in a randomized complete block design with 3 replications.

Susceptible variety BR11 was transplanted at 30 d after seeding (DAS)

Effect of fungicides on ShB and rice yield.^a BRRI, T. aman, 1987.

Treatment		Disease index	Yield at 14% moisture (t/ha)
Fungicide	Rate/ha		
Thiabendazole	1 liter	3.5 abc	4.1 a
Iprodione	1 kg	3.8 abc	3.9 ab
Thiabendazole + maneb	2.25 kg	5.5 a	3.7 b
Propiconazole	1 liter	2.0 cd	4.2 a
Thiophanate-methyl	2.25 kg	2.7 bc	3.4 c
Thiophanatemethyl + thiram	2.25 kg	3.2 bc	3.9 ab
Edifenphos	0.8 liter	4.8 ab	4.1 a
Control (inoculation, no spray)		5.7 a	3.4 c
CV (%)		15.6	7.5

^aMeans of 3 replications. In a column, figures followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 0.05 level (DMRT).

with 20- × 15-cm spacing. Recommended 60-40-40 kg NPK/ha was applied, using urea, triple

superphosphate, and muriate of potash. N was topdressed in 2 equal splits at 21 d after transplanting (DT) and before

panicle initiation; P and K were applied basally.

Rice plants were inoculated at panicle initiation to booting stage by placing 21-d-old culture of fungus grown in rice straw between the tillers of each hill at water level.

Fungicides were sprayed 7 d after

inoculation. Disease index (DI) data were recorded at maturity, yield was estimated from a central 2- × 1-m sample of each plot.

Propiconazole and thiophanate methyl + thiram significantly reduced disease severity, with corresponding

increases in yield (see table).

Thiophanate methyl decreased disease incidence with no increase in yield. With thiabendazole, iprodione, thiabendazole + maneb, and edifenphos, yield increased but disease did not decrease significantly. □

Effect of N and K on rice sheath rot (ShR) and crop yield

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We applied 5 levels of K, 1 level of P, and 2 levels of N in a 15-m² plot for a field trial. Incidence of ShR caused by *Sarocladium oryzae* (Sawada) Gam. was recorded 1 wk before harvest.

Disease incidence (DI) decreased with increased K (see table). Increasing the N level but with no change in P increased DI. □

Rice ShR and yield in Tamil Nadu, India.

Treatment (kg/ha) of			Disease incidence (%)	Decrease (%) over control	Grain yield (kg/plot)
N	P	K			
75	62.5	0	45	–	4.0
75	62.5	50	37	17	4.3
75	62.5	100	26	43	4.6
75	62.5	150	17	62	4.8
75	62.5	200	11	75	5.1
125	62.5	0	50	–	4.4
125	62.5	50	42	16	4.8
125	62.5	100	31	38	4.9
125	62.5	150	21	57	5.4
125	62.5	200	16	68	5.7
LSD (P = 0.01)			3		ns

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Insect management

Using mixtures of buprofezin and cypermethrin or deltamethrin for green leafhopper (GLH) and rice tungro virus (RTV) control

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Buprofezin, a slow-acting insectistatic compound, has high activity against *Nephotettix virescens* nymphs and is 50 to 100 times more effective than conventional insecticides. It is slow acting. It does not kill adult insects; only nymphs die during molting to the next instar. Deltamethrin and cypermethrin, which are pyrethroids, have quick knockdown effect on GLH adults.

Table 1. Field evaluation of buprofezin and deltamethrin for GLH control.^a IRRI, 1986.

Insecticide ^b	Rate (g ai/ha)	GLH (no./10 hills) ^c at 1 DAT				Hills (no.) showing RTV symptoms at 65 DT
		1st spraying		2d spraying		
		Adult	Nymph	Adult	Nymph	
Buprofezin 25 WP + deltamethrin 2.5 EC	50 + 6	1.3 ab	0.8 a	1.8 a	39.8 ab	7.5 bc
Buprofezin 25 WP + deltamethrin 2.5 EC	75 + 6	1.3 ab	0.5 a	1.8 a	29.5 ab	6.9 bc
Buprofezin 25 WP + deltamethrin 2.5 EC	6 + 13	1.0 ab	1.0 a	1.8 a	12.0 ab	5.0 bc
Buprofezin 25 WP + deltamethrin 2.5 EC	25 + 13	1.0 ab	0.5 a	0.3 a	15.0 ab	5.4 bc
Buprofezin 25 WP + deltamethrin 2.5 EC	75 + 13	1.0 ab	2.0 a	3.5 ab	8.5 a	5.0 bc
Buprofezin 25 WP	50	2.8 ab	28.8 b	3.3 ab	18.3 ab	10.8 bc
Buprofezin 25 WP	75	3.8 b	24.5 ab	7.0 bc	73.5 bc	13.0 b
Deltamethrin 2.5 EC	13	0.5 a	0.3 a	2.0 a	11.3 ab	6.0 bc
BPMC 50 EC	750	3.0 ab	15.5 ab	4.3 ab	34.8 ab	12.5 b
Untreated		4.0 b	20.0 ab	11.3 c	109.5 c	21.8 a

^a In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^b Insecticides were applied at 20, 35, 50, and 65 DT. Spray volume was 300-500 liters/ha. ^c Av of 4 replications. DAT = days after treatment.